

Module: Organisational Behaviour

Module code: 5302

Title: Self-reflection task

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1.0 Abstract

This reflection covers the reason for undertaking this module, as it is mainly from the interest of expanding my knowledge on organisational system through the lens of organisational behaviour. Additionally, this reflection provide insight on how the Brunei tradition and culture especially with MIB philosophy, along with UBD organisational culture shaped my ethics and professionalism.

2.0 Main Text

I have personally chosen the module to add to my knowledge on top of what has been covered in previous module, especially on management theory. I believe in the importance of conceptualising the impact of cultural and organisational behavior to decision making, provides further insight on organisational system and would hopefully prepare myself for professional workplace.

While for my personal development, national culture has highly influence me, especially with Melayu Islam Beraja (MIB) philosophy, with the focus on the value of Islamic teaching in governance, social, and development. Overall, it signifies the importance of characteristics such as respect, collectivism and a strong moral code. Consequently, my social interacting habit or behaviors, especially in professional settings with other people, are often rooted from the moral conduct of Islamic teaching and Malay tradition which are often viewed as gentle, polite and discrete. With these cultural values, I aspire to lead with professionalism and ethical consistency in my future career.

Meanwhile, Universiti Brunei Darussalam culture also impacted my learning behaviour, such that it is much more unstructured and more diverse in studying mode and method. Such learning experience promoted more independent learning, self-discipline and critical thinking in myself. Especially, in my previous undergraduate experience in UBD, adaptability skill was highly necessary during the Covid-19 lockdown and even post-lockdown, as there was a significant shift in the ways education was delivered, with more emphasis on assignment-based assessment and blended learning rather than examination. This experience has set my career perspective to prepare myself to work effectively in a more ever-changing workplace where continuous adjustment and self-discipline are very crucial. While in my Master's degree, the culture highlights the importance of collaboration, ethical, accountability, effective communication and responsibility.

Overall, UBD's organisational culture has changed my perspective to reframe challenges as opportunities for personal growth and to approach my future career with resilience, adaptability, and a commitment to learn continuously.